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Additional file 3: Figure S3. Scheme of AlphaLISA duplex assay for total and S129 phosphorylated human alpha-synuclein detection. The 4B12 antibody – binding to aa 103-108 – is biotinylated and used to bind the Streptavidin-coated Donor-beads. Terbium Acceptor beads were coupled to LB509 antibodies for total h-asyn quantification while the 11A5 antibody was used and attached to Europium Acceptor-beads in order to measure pS129 h-asyn. Both antibodies recognize an epitope close to each other (aa 115-122 and aa 129 respectively).